

PROSPECTS FOR THE INTRODUCTION OF AGROMARKETING IN THE AGROINDUSTRIAL COMPLEX

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***Abstract.** This article analyzes the development of marketing research in agriculture, taking into account modern challenges and trends. The main directions and methods of market research are considered, as well as their impact on the efficiency of managing agricultural enterprises. Particular attention is paid to new technologies such as data analytics and the use of digital marketing in the context of the development of the agricultural sector.*

***Keywords:** agriculture, marketing research, efficiency, management, technology, competitiveness, digital marketing.*

Introduction. In the system of market relations, agricultural enterprises cannot function normally without effective commercial activities related to market research, improving product quality, and managing the distribution and sales of manufactured products. There are trends in the development of science, production factors, and production relations, as well as in the strengthening of competition in the agricultural market, the increasing importance of agricultural raw materials for industry.

Literature analysis i . If we look at the marketing works of foreign authors F. Kotler, R. Evans, B. Berman, JJ Lambena and others, we will not find any special research on agricultural marketing. Therefore, we will try to answer, in our opinion, two important questions: first, what is agromarketing, and secondly, can it be used to solve the problems of the agrarian sector of the economy?

Any definition of marketing is fully consistent with agricultural marketing. In the book by R. Evans and B. Berman, marketing is defined as the anticipation, management and satisfaction of demand for goods, services, organizations, people, places and ideas through exchange. If we add marketing in agriculture to this definition, we get the definition of agromarketing. American professor F. Kotler gives a shorter, but no less comprehensive definition: "Marketing is a type of human activity aimed at satisfying needs and wants through exchange." It is these needs that are satisfied by agricultural products. American scientist R. Branson, analyzing important factors such as consumer behavior and people's purchasing power, describes agricultural marketing (agromarketing) as a set of all activities related to agricultural production and food, seeds, harvesting, processing, and delivery to the final consumer [1] .

The introduction of agromarketing creates the necessary conditions for the development of agromarketing systems and the regulation of market processes, creates conditions for identifying consumer demands and identifying opportunities to satisfy them, which in general helps to ensure food security and improve the living standards of the population of the region and the country [2].

The main goal of agromarketing management is to maintain a balance between the state of the marketing environment and the corresponding marketing activity system of the agricultural enterprise [3].

Research methodology. The research was carried out on the basis of statistical-economic, technical, institutional and profile reports, a study of the socio-economic, situation and development prospects of design, research, exploitation and other interested organizations. The article analyzes the main directions of agromarketing policy in agriculture, as one of the urgent issues of agricultural economists, using a wide range of scientific research methods.

Analysis and discussion of results.

With the development of market relations, the orientation of the enterprise's production processes to the requirements of the external environment becomes more relevant. The market is transformed from a position of setting conditions for producers to a point where the consumer has the opportunity to choose a product that meets his needs. In this case, the enterprise management must study the desires and needs of people in order to create the appropriate quality characteristics of the product.

The producer must take these factors into account when conducting economic activities, focusing on fully satisfying consumer needs and offering the necessary high-quality products, which, in turn, is ensured by developing an effective agromarketing policy.

The concept of agricultural marketing is a system of scientifically based views on the management of technological processes of production and sale of finished products, the provision of services to agricultural producers by the agro-industrial complex in market conditions. Marketing provides the intended results when it is directed to the full implementation of its functions and goals, primarily aimed at satisfying the needs and desires of customers in the market of goods and services, effectively using all elements of the marketing complex.

In such conditions, a sound approach to the implementation of agromarketing policy is necessary in terms of adapting to the changing market environment, which, in turn, includes all the specific features of agromarketing as a management system for agricultural enterprises and represents a system of scientifically based ideas for managing technological processes in agriculture.

The dependence of agricultural market performance on geographical factors, different forms of ownership, seasonality of harvest periods, and diversity of organizational forms of production and management indicate the different aspects of agromarketing from other types of marketing.

Agromarketing plays an important role not only in stimulating production and consumption, but also in accelerating the pace of economic development. The role and importance of the development of agromarketing are reflected in the following:

Optimizing resource use. An effective agromarketing system ensures the optimal use of resources in the production, processing and sale of agricultural products, which helps to reduce losses due to inefficient processing, storage and transportation on site. A well-thought-out marketing system ensures the efficient allocation of available stocks of commodity resources, thereby ensuring high growth rates in agriculture.

Increasing the income of agricultural enterprises . An effective agromarketing system improves the system of sales of agricultural products, reduces the number of intermediaries, ensures the supply of goods needed by consumers, ensures high incomes of agricultural producers, guarantees reasonable prices for agricultural products, which encourages the investment of idle assets in the purchase of modern means of production, and thereby contributes to increasing labor productivity.

Expanding sales markets. With the aim of more fully meeting needs, agromarketing allows you to expand the sales market for products, providing a sufficient supply of products to mass consumers, which contributes to the constant growth of demand for agricultural products.

Creation of new jobs. Expanding sales markets in the context of effectively created agromarketing will help create new jobs for the population engaged in the implementation of additional functions for the promotion of agricultural products (packaging, transportation, storage and processing), as well as attract farms, independent agricultural producers, traders, and retailers to the process.

Infrastructure development. Improving the agromarketing system requires the development of transport, logistics and trade infrastructure, which, by creating high demand for industrial products, serves as one of the important factors in the development of the economy of the country and the region.

Industrial development. Since agricultural products are widely used in the food, light, and chemical industries, improving the agromarketing system will directly impact these related sectors, giving a significant boost to their development.

Improving trade fair activities. Fair activities, which are an important factor of economic development based on the use of marketing tools and one of the levers of agromarketing, contribute to supporting the activities of local producers and establishing new economic relations. In addition to supporting local producers, fairs, being of social importance, help to increase the awareness of locally produced goods, promote new products, expand the assortment and reduce prices, and allow purchasing goods directly from the manufacturer at wholesale prices.

Thus, agromarketing, as a modern enterprise management system, helps to strengthen the market positions of agricultural producers, agricultural and commercial enterprises, as a tool that provides the ability of agricultural entities to adequately respond to the variability of the external environment in the market space.

Agromarketing is one of the most important areas of agribusiness. The measures included in the structure of agricultural marketing serve to fully implement the functions of agromarketing.

Taking the above into account, we can include the following among the functions of agromarketing in agriculture:

- a) exchange function (sale-purchase);
- b) physical function (storage, transportation, processing);
- c) production function (standardization, financing, risk acceptance and accounting, marketing research).

The main tasks of specialists working in the field of agromarketing are:

- Continuous organization of work as an agronomist and marketer;
- determining the actual prices of controlled products in agreement with the company's management body;
- creating a fair competitive environment that helps adapt to market demands;
- regulate marketing activities through standards and regulations;
- creating conditions for increasing the level of integration of agricultural production;
- monitoring compliance with established marketing practices and processes;
- risk management, providing marketing information, conducting marketing research and similar services;
- purchase, storage and resale of surplus products under control, etc.;

- creating more convenient mechanisms for lending to agricultural production and other activities in the agricultural marketing system.

In the modern context of adapting agromarketing to changing market conditions, the development and active use of scientific and technical achievements, the search for new forms of agromarketing activity in the market in order to better meet the demand of end consumers for agricultural products and services, is an important direction. This requires the expansion of agromarketing facilities through agro-innovations and agrotourism, which will allow the formation of modern directions of agromarketing.

Agro-innovation is the result of innovative activities aimed at creating new or improved agricultural products, using new technologies, and improving technological processes to ensure the effective use of agricultural potential.

Agricultural innovation marketing is the activity of developing, planning, and implementing innovative technologies in the agricultural sector of the economy, aimed at increasing the competitiveness of products to better meet the needs of the population.

Agroinnovations ensure the strengthening of the ecological orientation of agricultural and food enterprises, which is manifested in the development of new technologies to improve the quality and safety of food products, the introduction of cleaner and more efficient processes for the production and sale of agricultural products, waste recycling, etc.

Based on a review of information sources, foreign and domestic publications, official websites of specialized agencies, companies, trade unions, firms and enterprises, and partnerships that are part of the partners and associates in the agro-industrial complex, we present a systematic list of innovative technologies, including marketing technologies, that have allowed us to achieve significant positive results in the agricultural sector (Table 1).

Table 1

Modern innovative agromarketing technologies based on foreign experience

Naming	Description of technology
Information technology in agriculture	Information technology collects information about weather data, market prices, seasonal changes or shifts, local demand for goods, cultivation techniques, and profitable practices.
Technologies for determining soil fertility	To provide suggestions and recommendations to agricultural producers based on the collection and processing of soil data using modern technologies.
Nanotechnology in agriculture	A modern and innovative knowledge system for the modernization of agriculture using nanotechnology in agriculture, a scientific approach to the formation of healthy soil and the cultivation of healthy agricultural crops will be formed.
Soil and water sensors	They help determine the nitrogen content and moisture level in soil and crops, as well as other beneficial and necessary conditions and factors.
Precise land preparation	Precision farming is a new technology that uses satellite maps and computers to increase crop yields and reduce waste by analyzing the

	suitability of agricultural crops, fertilizers, and plant protection products for local soil conditions.
GPS GIS technology in agriculture	The use of GPS GIS technologies in the field of navigation leads to positive results and allows for uninterrupted operation in rural areas in adverse weather conditions.
Agricultural robots	The use of robots in the field allows for fast and error-free processing of land and crops.
Drones	Drones and unmanned aerial vehicles are widely used in agriculture today

Source: Compiled by the author based on literature analysis.

The introduction of new technologies into agriculture helps increase productivity, as well as reduce material and resource costs.

The creation of integrated information systems aimed at ensuring the flexible response of the agro-food complex to changing environmental conditions and the rational interaction of agromarketing elements with all elements of the enterprise management system will help increase the efficiency of agromarketing in modern business conditions (Figure 5.22).

In the formation of integrated information systems in agromarketing, the largest agricultural enterprises should create and implement modern, useful and attractive content to attract potential and interested buyers and consumers to the agricultural market, which implies the orientation of products and goods to the product and customer.

Conclusion. Research shows the need for consistent implementation of agromarketing in the sustainable development of agriculture, the conceptual basis of agromarketing is to support the sustainable development of agricultural producers and rural areas by expanding the markets for agricultural products.

The agromarketing business model developed during the research process is of great practical importance, its use provides agro-industrial enterprises with such advantages as standardization of business processes; improvement of work quality and business management; creation of the opportunity to purposefully improve activities; reduction of the dependence of business on the human factor, reduction of costs and increase of profits of agricultural enterprises.

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